

Research Paper

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THE ROLE OF UPI PAYMENT APPLICATIONS IN ENHANCING CONSUMER ENGAGEMENT WITH BRANDS

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Abstract

The study explores the role of UPI payment applications in improving consumer engagement with brands in the digital economy. The researcher has used primary research involving 300 respondents, the findings offer insights into how businesses can leverage UPI technology to enhance consumer engagement and increase their digital presence.

Keywords: UPI payment applications. Consumer Engagement

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INTRODUCTION

Technological innovations have led to gradual changes in digital payments in India in the last couple of years. The invention and innovation of smartphones and the internet have a major role in making India a cash-less society. The Indian citizens were not ready to adopt the rapidly changing technology due to a lack of trust in themselves. However, the GOI of India has welcomed reforms and made massive improvements to simplify payments.

The year 2016 is considered to be a milestone in the Indian economy as the NPCI and the Government of India jointly launched the UPI payment system which has become a vital part of many of the citizens in India. UPI is acting as the catalyst for economic and social improvements. (Ramachandran, 2018) The UPI is a system that makes many bank accounts into a single mobile application, including many banking features. The

UPI has reshaped the India's financial transaction landscape. (Ramachandran, 2018). The GOI has introduced the UPI to support its digitalization initiatives. It has enhanced financial inclusion and digital economy transition in India. UPI has not just emerged as an innovative technique in India but also in many other countries including Bhutan, France, North and South East Asia and many to be added.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

To analyze how UPI payment applications are driving marketing innovations and transforming consumer engagement in the digital economy.

RESEARCH QUESTION

How are UPI payment applications driving marketing innovations and enhancing consumer engagement in the digital economy?

HYPOTHESIS

H1: UPI payment applications have a significant positive impact on consumer engagement with brands.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The major advantage of UPI is it enhances financial literacy and inclusion in India. It also supports one of India's most valuable government schemes, PMJDY. In support to the above study, the UPI adoption has increased due to technological advancements and governmental support. (Neema & Neema, n.d.) The study also reveals that financial inclusion in turn drives economic development for the poor in India (Rastogi et al., 2021) (Shukla, 2024) (Ramachandran, 2018). In contradiction to the above study, one more study reveals that Financial Inclusion impacts the digital payment system. (Mrudula Bhimavarapu et al., 2022). India's digital payment future lies with the UPI and BHIM (Das & Das, 2017)

One more study states that digital payment usage in India increased during the COVID-19 outbreak by effectively addressing the challenges of traditional payment systems. (Ramachandran, 2018) It is also understood that the younger population has shifted towards digital payment platforms considering it to be safer and more secure. (Chaudhari & Kumar, 2021; Mate Chetan Dattaji Gaikwad & Kapdi Chetan Dattaji Gaikwad, n.d.)

It is also noted that consumers are increasingly adopting UPIs for digital transactions. We must also know that security concerns exist regarding mobile payments and banking information. (Devi & Indoria, n.d.; Indoria & Devi, n.d.-a) (Neema & Neema, n.d.). The government regulators must ensure UPI's cyber security and it is also important to create awareness and make UPI adoption nationwide. (Sankararaman & Suresh, n.d.)

In one of the studies, it was found that UPI is user-friendly and safer than other payment methods. It is due to customers' shift towards contactless payments that drives UPI's success. (Shukla, 2024) (Neema & Neema, n.d.). It is also noted that the users have a positive attitude toward the UPI payment applications (Indoria & Devi, n.d.-a)

We also cannot deny the fact that only 37% of users in India are partially aware of UPI functionalities and it is due to the ineffective advertising of the

UPI. More awareness is needed for rural customers than the urban customers because urban customers are already finding it easy to use the UPI applications. (Neema & Neema, n.d.) (Indoria & Devi, n.d.- b) (Baghla, 2018). When continuing with the study we can see that women are using less UPI due to the reason that they are less adaptable to new technology changes and even the daily UPI users are not motivated by the cashback. Even though people

The effect of Digital payment has impacted in such a way that ATM cash withdrawals have decreased by 15% and the digital payment volume has increased by 42% during the financial year of 2020/2021. (Chaudhari & Kumar, 2021).

In one study it is found that the cashless economy in India is becoming a reality. Still, in contradiction, the other study reveals the importance of cash transactions in India, stating that cash transactions may not disappear soon. (Rajendran & Sivabushanan, 2022)

Significance of the study

The current study focuses on the crucial aspect of modern consumer behaviour and marketing. It focuses on how UPI payment applications are reshaping the digital economy and transforming consumer engagement with their favourite brands.

METHODOLOGY

The study was qualitative and descriptive research aiming to know the role of UPI Payment Apps in Enhancing Consumer Engagement with Brands

Development of the tool

The researchers have developed a questionnaire of 17 questions divided into two parts. The first section includes demographic information, and the second section focuses on the Hypothesis based questions. The scoring of the survey is done using Likert scale.

The data was collected via an online survey, sending it to the urban users of UPI payment applications in Bengaluru.

Population and sample

The population consisted of 300 urban people who are using or aware of UPI payment applications and are the residents of Bengaluru.

Table 1: Demographic details

Demographics		Frequency	Percentage
Age	Below 18 years	4	1
	18-24 years	120	41
	25-34 years	110	38
	35-44	20	7
	45-54	33	11
	55 and above	5	2
Gender	Male	183	63
	Female	109	37
Education Level	High School	13	4
	Undergraduate	120	41
	Postgraduate	159	55
	Uneducated	0	0
Which UPI application do you use most frequently?	Google Pay	100	34
	PhonePe	180	62
How often do you use UPI application	Other	12	4
	Daily	115	39
	More than once a week	95	34
	Once a week	42	14
	Once a fortnight	30	10
	Once a month	10	3

OBSERVATIONS

Age Group & Gender Insights

- A majority of the users i.e 79% fall between the age group of 18-34 years, indicating the UPI payment apps in urban areas are primarily used by younger demographics
- It is also noted that there is a higher percentage of male users (63%) compared to female users (37%)

Education Level

- The data indicates a highly educated user base, with a majority (55%) with a qualification of postgraduation and 41% being undergraduates

UPI Application Preferences

- Phonepe is the most commonly used UPI application among users in urban areas, followed by Google Pay (34%). The other category makes up only 4%.

Usage Frequency

- A large number of users (73%) use UPI applications every day or at least once in a week which describes the frequent usage of UPI platform

DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis was performed using descriptive statistics, and regression analysis to assess the relationship between UPI and brand engagement.

Testing of the Hypothesis

The researchers have used the linear regression analysis to examine the relationship between UPI payment application usage and consumer engagement. The major goal was to test whether UPI payment applications significantly influence consumer engagement with brands. In the analysis part we have taken consumer engagement, measured on the prescribed scale, while the independent variable was the response to the given statement “ UPI payment applications made me more likely to engage with a brand after using their services.”

Table 2: Regression Output

Variable	Coefficients	Standard Error	p-value
Intercept	1.066	0.083	2.24E-30
Consumer engagement	0.153	0.066	0.021

Interpretation of the result

The research result for the hypothesis reveals that UPI payment applications majorly influence consumer engagement with brands. The coefficient

of 0.153 and p-value being 0.021 indicate a positive relationship between the use of UPI payment applications and consumer engagement with the brand. As the p-value is below the 0.05 threshold, confirming and suggesting that consumers who frequently use UPI are more likely to engage with the brands. So we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis which states UPI payment applications have a positive impact on consumer engagement with brands.

KEY FINDINGS

The overall findings reveal that UPI payment applications have a positive impact on consumer engagement with brands. The regression result shows that UPI usage correlates positively with consumer engagement indicated by a coefficient of 0.153 and a p-value of 0.021. It is also found in the research that consumers who frequently use UPI payment applications are more likely to use UPI payment apps while engaging with any of the brands due to the seamless, efficient, and secure nature of payment applications.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that UPI payment applications are important in transforming consumer engagement with brands in this digital era. It is also important for the brands to introduce the UPI into their payment offerings so that it can be helpful for them to build the customer base and also keep them engaged with their brand.

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